

A COMPLETE TEXT-TO-SPEECH SYSTEM FOR THE SLOVENIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The Slovenian text-to-speech engine is a modular system consisting of four independent modules (text normalization, grapheme-to-phoneme conversion, prosody generation and segmental concatenation), which are pipelined together. Each module is responsible for one portion of the problem of converting from text into speech. The first two modules comprises such tasks as end-of-sentence detection, abbreviation and number expansion, special formats conversion, morphological and contextual analysis, phonological modeling. In order to generate rules for our synthesis scheme, data was collected by analysing the readings of ten speakers, five males and five females. A two-level approach has been used for duration modelling and so-called superpositional approach at pitch modelling. The system is based on the concatenation of speech units, diphones and some frequently used polyphones, using TD-PSOLA technique.

1 INTRODUCTION

Speech synthesis, the automatic generation of speech waveforms, has developed rapidly in recent years [1, 2]. It is (or will be in the near future) used in various applications: in telecommunications, announcement and warning systems, telephone inquiry systems, for reading electronic mail, as aids for the blind or speaking-impaired, etc. The wider spread of these systems is bounded to some extent by the unnatural voice quality of most current synthesis systems. That particularly holds for smaller languages, where the degree of available knowledge is rather small.

The Slovenian text-to-speech (TTS) engine is a modular system consisting of several sequentially operating independent modules, as shown in Figure 1, which are pipelined together (<http://zlatoust.ijs.si/STTS/STTS.htm>). Each module is responsible for one portion of the problem of converting from text into speech. That enables easy improvements of separate parts of the system [4].

The input into the synthesizer is unconstrained text. In the first place of the hierarchical system architecture a text normalization module is located. It is followed by a grapheme-to-phoneme conversion and prosody generation module. At the end, a segmental concatenation module outputs a digital record of the synthetic speech which is produced by a computer sound card.

Figure 1. Slovene TTS system.

2 TEXT ANALYSIS

We use the phrase *text analysis* as a cover term for all of the computations involved in the first two modules of our synthesizer (the first and second level in Figure 1). That comprises such tasks as end-of-sentence detection, abbreviation and number expansion, special formats (hours, dates, addresses, telephone numbers, fractions, equations, roman numerals,...) conversion, morphological and contextual analysis, phonological modeling.

2.1 Text Normalization

With text preprocessing it is achieved that the input text is interpreted in a single manner. It is desired that a procedure is as robust as possible and that it does not assume any predefined text format.

The text normalizer first converts files in different formats into an ASCII file and removes all redundant symbols. Then, the following is performed:

- sentence-boundary detection,
- detection of abbreviations and special formats, like numbers, hours, dates, addresses, telephone numbers, fractions, equations, roman numerals, e-mail addresses, etc.,
- lemmatization: deriving uninflected (base) forms from inflected words,
- part-of-speech assignment,
- abbreviation expansion and special formats conversion,
- accentuation by using accentual schemes.

The input text is analysed sentence by sentence. The sentence is considered every sequence of graphemes which end with ending punctuation mark (dot, question mark, exclamation mark, three dots, EOF – end of file). The dot is not always considered as the ending punctuation mark, such as end of abbreviation, decimal point, ordinal numerals, dates.

Slovenian language is especially difficult to analyze, because of its morphological complexity. In contrast to some other languages, it is very important that we do a part-of-speech assignment at the beginning of the text normalization procedure. This information is inevitably needed for correct abbreviation expansion and special format conversion. Some examples:

- The correct form of the percentage symbol % in Slovenian language depends on complex contextual factors. The first decision that needs to be made is whether the number-percent string is modifying a following noun. Then the word *odstotek* have to be in the adjectival form and it must also agree in gender, case and number with the following noun. The number must occur in nominative form. For example, the correct rendition of *z 10% popustom* (with ten percent discount) is *z deset [nom] odstotnim [dat, sg, mas] popustom [dat, sg, mas]*. If the percentage expression does not modify a following noun, the nominal form *odstotek* is used. This form appears in different cases and numbers depending upon the number it occurs with. For example *en [nom, sg] odstotek [nom, sg]* (one percent), *dva [nom, dual] odstotka [nom, dual]* (two percent), *trije [nom, pl]; štirje [nom, pl] odstotki [nom, pl]* (three, four percent), *pet [nom, pl] odstotkov [gen, pl]* (five percent). This presumes that the percentage expression is in a non-oblique case. If the expression is in an oblique case, then both the number and *odstotek* show up in that case, with *odstotek* being in the singular if the number is one, dual if the number is two, and the plural otherwise (*s petimi [instr, pl] odstotki [instr, pl]* - with five percent). The problem is similar as in the Russian language [3]. However, in Slovenian language additional complication represents the fact that along with singular and plural also dual has to be taken into account.

To correctly expand this form we must do a substantial amount of analysis of the context (morphological

properties and an analysis of the relationship of the percentage expression to the surrounding words). When more possibilities are available the one which is considered as the most frequent is chosen.

- By abbreviation expansion an attention must be taken that the word represented in its full form is in the correct gender, number and case: i.e. *g. Janezu* (Mr. John) can be converted to *gospodu [dat, sg] Janezu [dat, sg]*; *str. 5* (page five) can be converted to *stran [nom, sg] pet [nom, sg], strani [gen, sg] pet [gen, sg]* etc.
- Similar holds for numerals: *25. april* (25th of April) can be converted to *petindvajseti [nom, sg] april [nom, sg]* and *25. aprila* (25th of April) to *petindvajsetega [gen, sg] aprila [gen, sg]*.

The most difficult part of the text analysis in Slovenian language is the correct stress assignment, since it can be located almost arbitrarily on any syllable. The stress of some words can also change with different cases. Accentual schemes describe those changes in detail. An example is shown in Figure 2.

Dictionary record for the noun <i>steber</i> [mas] (column):		
stebèr -brà [stɔ̀bèr] m (¶ ä)		
Accentual scheme for this record:		
sg. nom.	gen.	dat.
~Ø	-à	-ù
stebèr	stebrà	stebrù
sg. accu.	loc.	inst.
~Ø	-ù	-òm
stebèr	stebrù	stebròm
dual nom.	gen.	dat.
-à	-òv and -óv	-oma
stebrà	stebròv (óv)	stèbroma
dual accu.	loc.	inst.
-à	-ih	-oma
stebrà	stebrìh	stèbroma
pl. nom.	gen.	dat.
-ì	-òv and -óv	-òm
stebrì	stebròv (óv)	stebròm
pl. accu.	loc.	inst.
-è	-ih	-ì
stebrè	stebrìh	stebrì

Figure 2. An example of usage of accentual schemes for noun *steber* (column).

An extensive dictionary of 300,000 uninflected words is used which includes the location as well as the type of the lexical stress and tonemic accent. With the use of rules and accentual schemes we can derive more than 3.5 millions different word forms. The exceptions which do not follow the known rules are included in the separate dictionary. For rare words that fail to get analysed by these means, another special set of rules was developed. In this case the stress is predicted regarding the number of syllables within the

word, the position and the context of the possibly accented vowels, and the lists of stressable and unstressable affixes, prefixes and suffixes.

At the end, the whole text is segmented into individual words with additional information (lexical stress, tonemic accent, grammatical part-of-speech) and basic punctuation marks.

2.2 Grapheme-to-Phoneme Conversion

A grapheme-to-phoneme module produces strings of phonemic symbols from the normalized text. Word pronunciation including:

- detection and analysis of homographs,
- pronunciation of names and ordinary words.

Once the stress location is known it is very easy to convert the word into its phonetic representation. That is done on the basis of the known stress type, grammatical part-of-speech information and use of rules [5]. Most of this context-dependent letter-to-sound rules were composed by well-versed linguists [6], Figure 3.

An excerpt of the rules for <i>reduced vowel e (@)</i> : (\$ – end of word)		
XYec\$ → XY@c\$	:- noun, nom., sg., X ≠ @, Y ≠ [l r]	
XYen\$ → XY@n\$	:- adj., nom., sg., X ≠ @, Y ≠ [l r]	
XeYZ → X@YZ	:- not_sonant(X), sonant(Y), cons(Z)	
XeYWZ → X@YWZ	:- not_sonant(X), Y ≠ [lj nj], cons(Z)	
...		

Figure 3. An example of letter-to-sound rules.

The Slovenian word <i>je</i> has two meanings: <i>jè</i> (verb <i>to be</i>) or <i>jé</i> (verb <i>to eat</i>).		
Rules	Pronunciation	Example
...	...	...
<i>to + je</i>	⇒ <i>jè</i> (verb <i>to be</i>)	To je stol. (This is a chair.)
<i>koliko + je</i>	⇒ <i>jè</i> (verb <i>to be</i>)	Koliko je ura? (What's the time?)
...	...	...
<i>je + noun</i> _[fem, nom]	⇒ <i>jè</i> (verb <i>to be</i>)	Ona je lepa. (She is beautiful.)
<i>je + noun</i> _[fem, accu]	⇒ <i>jé</i> (verb <i>to eat</i>)	On je čokolado. (He is eating a chocolate.)
<i>on + je + noun</i> _[mas or neu, (meaning ≠ food)]	⇒ <i>jè</i> (verb <i>to be</i>)	On je pilot. (He is a pilot.)
<name> + <i>je + noun</i> _[mas or neu, (meaning = food)]	⇒ <i>jé</i> (verb <i>to eat</i>)	Janez je sendvič. (John is eating a sandwich.)
...	...	...

Figure 4. Partial rules for the homograph *je*.

By detection and analysis of homographs a special dictionary is used which includes basic meaning for about 5,000 nouns, and corresponding rules. The rules were obtained by hand on the basis of collected examples. An example of this procedure is shown in Figure 4.

3 PROSODY GENERATION

The proper choice of prosodic parameters, given by phoneme duration and intonation contours, enables natural sounding high quality synthetic speech.

Data was collected by analyzing the readings of 10 speakers. All of them are native Slovene speakers, five males and five females. The largest part of the speech material consists of declarative sentences in short stories, monologues, news, weather reports and commercial announcements. Other parts of the corpora are interrogative sentences with yes/no and wh-questions and imperative sentences.

Prosodic parameters are set (the third level in Figure 1) in three steps: duration assignment, pitch assignment and insertion of pauses.

3.1 Duration Modelling

A *two-level approach* has been used for duration modelling. The *intrinsic duration* of words [7] is determined by using factors such as phone name, phone type, phone context, segmental identity, syllable type and syllabic stress. The higher-level rhythmic and structural constraints of a phrase predict the *extrinsic duration* of a word. The following factors have been taken into account: the chosen speaking rate, the word's position within a phrase and the number of syllables within a word. At the end, intrinsic segment durations are modified, so that the entire word achieves its predetermined extrinsic duration [8].

3.2 Pitch Modelling

The F0 contour is defined with the function composed from [9]: a global component and local components.

The *global component* gives the baseline for the F0 contour for the whole intonation unit. It depends on the type of the intonation unit, position of the intonation unit in a complex sentence with two or more intonation units and duration of the whole intonation unit.

The *local components* present local movements of the F0 shape at accented syllables or syntactic boundaries. Tonemic accent in Slovenian language is signed by a pitch rise within a stressed syllable, followed by a fall, which depends on the accent (acute or circumflex) and syllable (baritone or ocsitone).

Many functions were tested (linear, power, transfer, decay, exponential) for the best approximation of the natural F0 contour [10]. In the system presented, an exponential function for the global component and a cosinusoidal function for accents and final boundary contours were adopted.

3.3 Pauses

In the analyzed readings pauses represent 18 % of the whole database duration. They are classified into four groups with respect to types and durations: at prefaces and new paragraphs, at the end of sentences, at places of prosodic phrases in the sentences and at places of rhythmical divisions of the clause, often before the conjunction of Slovene words *in*, *ter* (and), *pa* (but), *ali* (or), ...

The obtained results show that pause duration is almost independent of the duration of the intonation unit before the pause, only duration of the pauses greatly depends on whether there is breathing in or not [10]. The stochastic variance in the range of pause durations prevents the synthetic, discrete nature of pauses in synthetic speech.

4 SEGMENTAL CONCATENATION

An analysis of the Slovenian phonological system gives 8 vowel and 21 consonant phonemes. When adding allophonic variations for some phonemes, we arrived at a total of 40 phones. One diphone for every allophone combination possible in a given language is required. Our diphone inventory contains 1680 pitch-labeled diphones. They were hand-segmented and hand-labeled in order to enable as good as possible coupling at concatenation points. In order to guarantee high synthesis quality, the diphones were recorded by a professional speaker and placed in the middle of logatoms, pronounced with a steady intonation [4]. Currently we are adding some larger units to the existent diphone inventory: polyphones and frequently used short words (about 2000 most frequent Slovene words and 400 words from the fields of employment, whether reports, traffic information, etc.). This way, the final quality of the synthetic speech would be much better.

By assembling elemental speech units (the last level in Figure 1) we used a concatenative TD-PSOLA technique [11], improved with a variable length linear interpolation process [12]. This algorithm enables pitch and duration transformations directly on the waveform, at least for moderate ranges of prosodic modifications without considerably affecting the quality of synthesized speech. In contrast to the pure TD-PSOLA algorithm it also supports spectral interpolation between voiced parts of segments [12].

5 CONCLUSION

We developed a complete TTS system for the Slovenian language based on the acoustical units concatenation. The experiment showed that the system is an appropriate tool for generating audible speech from text in the Slovenian language [4].

Sound examples are available on the web page: <http://zlatoust.ijs.si/STTS/STTS.htm> along with the on-line version of the synthesiser: <http://zlatoust.ijs.si/OnlineSynthesis/SpeechOnline.htm>.

The advances in technology and new methods have already enriched practical usefulness so that our system can

be used in practical tasks such as the EMA employment agent [13]. The quality of the system is still inferior to human speech, but the improvements are clearly noticeable.

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